

Supplementary Material

Fig. S1 - The cytogenetic map of polymorphic and fixed inversions between *An. messeae*/*An. daciae* and *An. atroparvus* (modified from Artemov et al., 2021). The X00 and X11 are polymorphic inversion arrangements in *An. messeae* and *An. daciae*. The *An. atroparvus* X chromosome has two fixed inversions in comparison with the X11 arrangement of *An. messeae*.

Fig. S2 - Scheme of iterative mapping.

Table S1. – The *An. atroparvus* genes are used as markers for physical mapping of breakpoint regions of fixed rearrangements in the X chromosome of *An. messeae*.

Nº	VectorBase gene name	Primers sequences (5' -> 3')	Genomic location in AatrE3 : start	Genomic location in AatrE3: end	<i>An. atroparvus</i> chromosome regions	<i>An. messeae</i> chromosome regions
1	AATE010696	gcgtaaagcacgttccaaat	AatrE3_X:18,023	22,191(+)	1A	1A
		gacgggaagcaacttcag				
2	AATE001169	tggaggacgttcggttctg	AatrE3_X:1,162,806	1,170,169(+)	1A	1A
		aattccgactgctcgctagg				
3	AATE008844	agttcgtgactcgcaggtg	AatrE3_X:1,447,542	1,458,895(+)	1B	1B
		tgctgttgctgcgttttcg				
4	AATE011784	tgtttaacctcgtcgttg	AatrE3_X:1,463,880	1,465,754(+)	1B	Multiple
		ggtacttcgagtcgttggtg				
5	AATE016042	ttgctcttaggttcggaatg	AatrE3_X:1,465,925	1,468,608(-)	1B	4B

		gggctatgttactgggtcta				
6	AATE002683	tctcacttttcgtaagccc	AatrE3_X:1,474,565	1,477,429(-)	1B	4B
		cagctcgtggtagtagaaca				
7	AATE009927	caggctagcgtgaaaaat	AatrE3_X:1,503,333	1,512,052(+)	1B	4B
		catactggcgtcttatgcac				
8	AATE012122	tgtgacgaactttaccggg	AatrE3_X:1,514,581	1,519,283(-)	1B	4B
		gcgactgatgacgatga				
9	AATE009073	acttcgatcgcgtcctc	AatrE3_X:1,564,139	1,566,618(+)	1B	4B
		cttcggcgcggagta				
10	AATE013780	ccagtggacggagctaaatc	AatrE3_X:1,629,871	1,633,254(+)	1B	4B
		ggatggactgtatcgctgt				
11	AATE017741	gcagctgttatgtcctcgg	AatrE3_X:1,960,425	1,963,110(+)	1B	4B
		gtagtacaccagtagcgcc				
12	AATE016081	tcgagtgccggtgataaag	AatrE3_X:1,978,577	1,981,869(+)	1B	4B
		agggagttatcacatgacgg				
13	AATE020982	tgcatagtgaagacacctc	AatrE3_X:1,983,088	1,985,780(+)	1B	4B
		agaccttagcatatcgccag				
14	AATE016478	cctctcatcatcgcgaaaaa	AatrE3_X:1,988,001	1,992,840(-)	1B	4B
		catacgacatgctggatcg				
15	AATE020848	tcacaagcgtacgagtacat	AatrE3_X:1,999,834	2,001,318(+)	1B	1C
		cattgctcagtaaacggag				
16	AATE001684	acgggtgtgaactcctaac	AatrE3_X:2,012,649	2,015,622(-)	1B	1C
		cagaatgtcctcgtatctct				
17	AATE002246	agaaaggaggctactacga	AatrE3_X:2,028,585	2,041,909(-)	1B	1C
		ggaaatcgtcgtagcggaaa				
18	AATE017108	gatcgtgcaggcacagtcta	AatrE3_X:2,352,907	2,358,255(+)	1C	1C
		tcgtagatcgaacaagtcg				
19	AATE010870	ccaaatcttcaatcgcccg	AatrE3_X:2,927,563	2,928,974(+)	1C	1C
		cgtaagtcgtctcggaat				
20	AATE012020	acattctgcatctcgcacag	AatrE3_X:4,602,182	4,608,814(-)	2A	2A
		catcacgtcggggaagtagt				
21	AATE015765	cccgaaaaacatagcccga	AatrE3_X:5,527,302	5,531,343(-)	2B	2B
		aaccggttgaacgttgat				
22	AATE000795	gctgaaaaccgatccgatgc	AatrE3_X:6,504,256	6,513,151(-)	2B	2B

		cacttacggcgatcctcctc				
23	AATE004111	gtggaactacaacggccaga	AatrE3_X:8,538,061	8,542,551(-)	2C	2C
		agattgggcagaaaggcgaa				
24	AATE001403	gactttgccacactgctgaa	AatrE3_X:8,751,285	8,754,177(-)	2C	2C
		tctccattcgcatatcctc				
25	AATE018270	gcacggggtcttcaacagta	AatrE3_X:9,855,878	9,857,040(+)	3B	3B
		agccgggtgagaacatcagg				
26	AATE017493	cggttcgcttcatagcttgc	AatrE3_X:10,389,518	10,398,371(+)	3B	3B
		ccgtgctccgtaactgtctt				
27	AATE008369	ggtttctccagcccgtactc	AatrE3_X:11,111,502	11,114,625(+)	3B	3B
		gatggtgctgcaggtggtag				
28	AATE021170	atccaggcgatcattagccg	AatrE3_X:11,446,721	11,457,749(+)	3C	3C
		cctccgctatcggtttacc				
29	AATE018218	gttcccggacgaacagttta	AatrE3_X:11,958,281	11,959,687(-)	3C	4A
		cagcttgaagtggatga				
30	AATE002004	atgcctcctgatacgag	AatrE3_X:12,042,801	12,043,277(-)	3C	4A
		taacgtggcattaccattg				
31	AATE005108	aagtgtgcggtcacgagtc	AatrE3_X:12,069,346	12,075,734(+)	3C	Multiple
		ggacggcacgatctaagagg				
32	AATE002819	cgcagcttaacatctcgtc	AatrE3_X:12,312,468	12,315,265(-)	3C	4A
		ccattggaagccattggtag				
33	AATE000407	gtcatctcgcacatactgtt	AatrE3_X:12,347,972	12,350,706(-)	3C	4A
		tactactaaggtaggcggtt				
34	AATE002183	catcagcgtgttctcgttac	AatrE3_X:12,360,652	12,374,345(-)	3C	1C
		cagtagcgactccttgagac				
35	AATE005101	ctgcctagagacgatccg	AatrE3_X:12,383,120	12,391,835(+)	3C	1C
		gctagcgttcacaacatcc				
36	AATE005236	cggggcaacatcctattggt	AatrE3_X:12,437,092	12,444,184(-)	3C	3C
		ttccacaactgatggctcc				
37	AATE016801	cgctcagaagctcgatccat	AatrE3_X:13,084,169	13,097,940(+)	3C	3C
		tattctgccgatccagcgac				
38	AATE009941	cgctgttccgtgattttctac	AatrE3_X:13,261,242	13,265,420(+)	4A	1C
		cttcttcccaccgttcgag				
39	AATE016644	gctgttcaacctgatcgac	AatrE3_X:13,405,667	13,414,963(+)	4A	1C

		gaagtgcctataggagtcgtg				
40	AATE010434	taagttgcaccgtgacctc	AatrE3_X:13,484,949	13,487,325(+)	4A	1C
		tctggcgggagataagaca				
41	AATE003509	catatgccgagcatcac	AatrE3_X:13,604,821	13,616,218(-)	4A	1B
		ccgacttgaccgttctatg				
42	AATE015407	gtacaacctggacgtgttg	AatrE3_X:14,122,043	14,125,830(+)	4A	1B
		gcattcgttggaagaagt				
43	AATE011319	cctggtgcaatggtctact	AatrE3_X:14,267,272	14,271,819(+)	4A	1B
		ttgatccatggacgacgg				
44	AATE004133	cttctatcaactcgactgcg	AatrE3_X:14,442,250	14,444,588(-)	4A	1B
		tacttcgggaagagctagg				
45	AATE004183	agaaatacaagagtgcccg	AatrE3_X:14,480,893	14,510,197(+)	4A	1B
		ggatgagcggagaggaaaa				
46	AATE009858	gcaccgcaagaaga	AatrE3_X:14,520,988	14,521,746(+)	4A	4B
		gcacgaagctcggaa				
47	AATE009010	agctacaccagggaactgac	AatrE3_X:14,525,064	14,530,105(-)	4A	4B
		accgttggtattctccgct				
48	AATE021145	gtgaagaaccagacgcttac	AatrE3_X:14,584,043	14,588,240(-)	4A	4B
		aggaagtacggatagttcgg				
49	AATE007306	ccatgctgtgtcattagg	AatrE3_X:14,680,861	14,684,961(+)	4A	4B
		tcgttcgtgtactgctctat				
50	AATE005256	gactacgtgatacagatcgc	AatrE3_X:14,795,318	14,811,135(-)	4A	4B
		tggccttcggtagtag				
51	AATE018661	gcgaggagctgatacagacc	AatrE3_X:15,491,805	15,495,758(-)	4A	4B
		ttcttctgcgctccttgat				
52	AATE010210	tgaccaactaccgactgtgc	AatrE3_X:15,918,625	15,921,507(-)	4B	4B
		gtaagcctcaacgcttct				
53	AATE016157	gtgaccaagcgagtagtct	AatrE3_X:16,324,241	16,326,290(-)	4B	4B
		ggtaagtccggcgattga				

Fig. S3 – Density of simple repeats in the BRs and approximately 100-kb genomic neighborhoods of the BRs in the X chromosome of *An. atroparvus*. Light pink bars show the position of BRs within genomic neighborhoods. Red and blue bars show the density of simple repeats in BRs and genomic neighborhoods, respectively. Genomic neighborhoods are defined as 50-kb genomic regions located immediately upstream and downstream of each BR. λ is a mean density of simple repeats over the entire chromosome with bin size equal to corresponding BR size.

Fig. S4 – Gene density in the BRs and approximately 100-kb genomic neighborhoods of the BRs in the X chromosome of *An. atroparvus*. Light pink bars show the position of BRs within genomic neighborhoods. Red and blue bars show the gene density in BRs and genomic neighborhoods, respectively. Genomic neighborhoods are defined as 50-kb genomic regions located immediately upstream and downstream of each BR. λ is a mean density of genes over the entire chromosome with bin size equal to corresponding BR size.